

A Thallimetric Oxidation Method for the Estimation of Tartronic Acid

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Tartronic acid (hydroxymalonic acid), the first oxidation product of malonic acid¹, has some biological significance². A method has been developed for the isolation and identification of tartronic acid and utilised for its quantitative assay in urine and tissues based on ion-exchange and paper chromatography³. But so far no convenient titrimetric method is available for the estimation of tartronic acid.

The present authors in an earlier investigation observed tartronic acid as the first intermediate product in the oxidation of malonic acid by thallium(III)¹ that was subsequently found to get oxidised to carbon dioxide and water. Based on these observations, the authors thought of the possibility of a convenient method for the determination of tartronic acid by thallium(III) which is described here.

Results and Discussion

The reaction between thallium(III) and tartronic acid is monitored by titrating the thallium(I) formed with potassium bromate using methyl orange (or brilliant ponceaux 5R) as indicator. Tartronic acid does not interfere in this titration.

The photochemical thallimetric oxidation reaction is investigated in 1.0 M perchloric acid medium in the presence of varying concentrations of thallium(III). The photochemical oxidation of tartronic acid under the conditions does not result in complete quantitative oxidation. These results could not be improved even in the presence of bromide ion

which in low concentrations was found to be a very good catalyst in thallimetric photochemical oxidations. So the thermal reaction is investigated.

Perchloric acid solutions of high concentrations when heated at high temperature especially in the presence of organic substances, are likely to cause explosions. Hence, perchloric acid medium was avoided for these studies and sulphuric acid medium was used. The effect of thallium(III) concentration on the oxidation of tartronic acid in 1.5 M sulphuric acid medium was investigated.

The results indicate that the oxidation of tartronic acid is similar to malonic acid¹. Only in the presence of large excess of thallium(III) and after reflux for 120 min, the quantitative oxidation takes place. The experiments conducted to know the effect of acid concentration, indicated that quantitative oxidation takes place only when the concentration of sulphuric acid is 1.5 M or above. Tartronic acid is reported¹ to be the first thermal thallimetric oxidation product of malonic acid under similar conditions.

Experimental

An aqueous solution of tartronic acid was prepared and standardised by the ceric sulphate method⁴. Thallium(III) solutions were prepared and standardised as described earlier⁵.

The photochemical reactions were carried out using a Phillips high pressure mercury vapour lamp (200–250 V, 125W) as the light source. The thermal

reactions were carried out by refluxing the reaction mixture.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing 0.02–0.10 mmol of tartronic acid, thallium(III) (1.6 mmol) and sufficient H₂SO₄ were added so that the overall concentration of the mixture became 1.5 M and diluted to 75 ml. It was refluxed for 120 min, cooled to 60°, followed by the addition of HCl (15 ml) and 0.1% brilliant ponceaux 5R indicator (0.1 ml). The thallium(I) formed was then titrated with 0.00829 M (1.392 g dm⁻³) potassium bromate until the indicator colour disappeared.

References

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